

Teacher Supervision Strategy in Maintaining Learning Quality in Kindergarten using the Montessori Method

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ABSTRACT

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The quality of ECE (Early Childhood Education) implementation determines the quality of the processes within it, teachers have an important role in education, teacher professionalism and the quality of learning will increase if supervision is carried out with a clear structure and direction. In kindergarten, many schools label the name Montessori even though the education is far from the Montessori education method. The aim of this research is to analyze ECE teacher supervision strategies, implementation of learning using the Montessori method, and supervision strategies using the Montessori method. This research uses a qualitative approach of the SLR type, the PRISMA model. The process involves: (1) Searching for articles using the Google Scholar search engine, (2) Determining inclusion and exclusion criteria, (3) Screening until inclusion articles that meet the criteria are collected, (4) Synthesis of relevant literature to get a comprehensive picture of the related issues. Teacher supervision strategies to maintain the quality of learning using the Montessori method in PAUD/ECE. Teachers are child educators who provide stimulation, so that "Montessori Schools" must be given supervision regarding teacher supervision. The results of this research: In Indonesia, educational evaluation is carried out through monitoring and evaluation activities (Monev) or supervision carried out by education and evaluation supervisors who are accredited by the National Accreditation Agency (BAN), then learning using the Montessori Method has 4 pillar concepts and 9 elements, and The supervision strategy using the Montessori method for teachers is that the prerequisites are supervision with knowledge, interpersonal skills and technical skills.

KEYWORDS:

Strategy, Supervision, Teacher, Quality of Learning, Early Childhood education, Montessori.

1. INTRODUCTION

Creating a learning environment and procedure that allows students to develop their potential—including their religious and spiritual power, self-control, personality, intelligence, and noble morals—as well as the skills they will need for both themselves and society is what education is all about (UU SISDIKNAS No.20, 2003). Early childhood education (PAUD) is the phase of education given to children from birth until they enter formal education such as kindergarten.

In a stimulating setting, early childhood education focuses on children's social, emotional, cognitive, linguistic, artistic, and physical motor development. Since each of these

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factors is connected to the others and plays a crucial part in stimulating the brain, none of them should be disregarded. With the correct guidance, young children may lay a solid foundation for lifelong learning. Government Regulation 17 Article 61 of 2010 regulating the Management and Implementation of Early Childhood Education, functions, and objectives, explains the goals of early childhood education: (1) laying the groundwork for students' future development as human beings with faith in God Almighty, noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, innovative, independent, self-confident morals, and the ability to become responsible, democratic citizens; and (2) fostering children's potential in terms of their spiritual, intellectual, emotional, kinesthetic, and social intelligence during their formative years/golden years in an environment that is both stimulating and educational.

The execution of Indonesia's early childhood education program determines its overall excellence. A strong curriculum, instructors, literature, media, parental support, and community involvement are all necessary to promote

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learning. Nevertheless, a lot of Indonesian early childhood education facilities haven't actually implemented these changes (Herlina et al., 2023).

Teachers play a significant role in formal education by providing stimulus for components of early childhood development. Teachers hold a critical position in preparing the nation's future by successfully educating children with the necessary knowledge to shape children's character into noble individuals with high teaching ethics who are prepared to compete with the rest of the world (Belan & Niron, 2021). Teachers serve as learning facilitators, motivators, role models, mentors, collaborators, inventors, and assessors as a kind of evaluation for pupils. Teachers are an important resource for meeting one of the ideal components of early childhood education implementation. According to Minister of National Education Regulation No. 16 of 2007 about Academic Qualification Standards and Teacher Competency, teacher competency includes personality, pedagogical, professional, and social competence.

Organized and directed supervision improves teacher's professional qualities and the quality of learning (Ali & May, 2023). Supervisors in the Indonesian education system perform administrative tasks such as educational supervision, managerial oversight, professional guidance, and teacher and principal training (Basuki & Perdinanto, 2023). Education in schools must have clear and realistic planning, be effective and efficient in organizing, providing direction and motivation for all school personnel so that the quality of their performance always improves, and be monitored to ensure that school goals are achieved and carried out in a long-term manner (Marhawati, 2018).

The challenge is that research on academic monitoring for kindergarten is still insufficient (Herlina et al., 2023). There are schools that use unstructured supervision with no systematic implementation by the principal, and teachers do not receive direction to develop their talents in controlling the learning process (Babo & Syamsuddin, 2022). Some teachers focus on theory rather than (Puroila et al., 2021). Many schools describe themselves as "Montessori," despite the fact that Montessori has its own curriculum. Schools that label themselves as "Montessori" must grasp the Montessori method, and teachers are trained to convey knowledge about the Montessori method. Because of the free use of the name Montessori, numerous institutions are using it, even if they have nothing to do with Montessori education (Tuross, 2024). Not all 'Montessori' schools properly adhere to Montessori principles, have trained Montessori teachers, or are accredited by professional bodies (Marshall, 2017). Many Montessori schools use the term but do not follow AMI (Association Montessori Internationale) guidelines.

This study investigates teacher supervision options for sustaining the quality of learning in kindergarten using the Montessori Method, employing a systematic literature review

(SLR) to address the challenges that have been identified. The purpose of this systematic literature review (SLR) is to examine kindergarten teacher supervision tactics, Montessori-based learning implementation, and Montessori-based supervision strategies.

II. METHOD

Research Approach

This research uses a qualitative approach of the SLR (Systematic Literature Review) type by synthesizing relevant literature in order to obtain a comprehensive picture regarding teacher supervision strategies to maintain the quality of learning using the Montessori method in PAUD. The data source was obtained through Google Scholar and a search strategy using the keywords "strategy, PAUD teacher supervision, Montessori method".

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Literature search using the Google Scholar search engine. The inclusion criteria sought were: (1) Specific topics discussing teacher supervision, PAUD teacher supervision, PAUD supervision strategies, Montessori teacher training, (2) Using certain journals that have Sinta and Scopus indexation, (3) Articles spanning the last 10 years. The exclusion criteria are: (1) Articles with irrelevant topics, (2) Journals that do not have indexation, (3) Time period 2017-2024.

Systematic Mapping

This research uses the Systematic Literature Review Prisma flow, starting by searching for articles using the Google Scholar search engine, then determining inclusion and exclusion criteria, the prism flow starts from identification, screening until inclusion articles that meet the collected criteria.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 1 (Prisma Diagram)

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Table Data found during identification from databases (n = 30,381) and registers (n = 100), then removed before screening (n = 11,326), then screening was carried out, when screening the remaining data from identification (n = 17,155), screening records were carried out excluded (n = 16,855), reports sought for retrieval (n = 300), reports not retrieved (n = 250), reports assessed for eligibility (n = 50). The explanation for the excluded data is due to the long period (n = 14,321) and irrelevant topics (n = 16,200). So, the number of articles or data included for the review study is (n = 50).

Based on the included articles produced through PRISMA, the main contents can be summarized as presented in Table 1.

No	Penulis	Judul dan Jurnal	Hasil
1	(Utami et al., 2020)	Evaluasi Program Pengelolaan Lembaga PAUD di Kabupaten Serang	Educators and education personnel need to improve their abilities, and supervisors or supervisors of related institutions and agencies must be more concerned about supervising and developing these institutions so that education is better.
		Jurnal: Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini (S2)	
2	(Botutihe, 2020)	Pola Pengelolaan Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini di Kota Gorontalo	Research indicates 85% good management in early childhood education in Gorontalo City, utilizing technical, personality, and social competence of administrators, educators, and staff to positively impact children's development.
		Jurnal: Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini (S2)	
3	(Pujiyati, 2021)	Kepemimpinan Pendidikan	Field findings show that

		Masa Pandemi Covid-19 Pada Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini	teachers still experience low motivation. This can be caused by inappropriate curricula, suboptimal learning processes, and inadequate funding.
		Jurnal: Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini (S2)	
4	(Rasmani et al., 2021)	Manajemen Soft Skills Guru dalam Menguatkan Mutu Pembelajaran di PAUD	Research indicates that teachers' soft skills, including pedagogical competence, personality, and professionalism, significantly influence the quality of PAUD institutions, emphasizing the importance of effective management.
		Jurnal: Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini (S2)	
5	(Rasmani et al., 2023)	Manajemen Pembelajaran Proyek pada Implementasi Kurikulum Merdeka di Lembaga PAUD	At Al Khoir Kindergarten Surakarta, the independent curriculum designed using project-based learning methods has been implemented well from start to finish. In implementing the P5 project at Al Khoir Kindergarten Surakarta, parental involvement and character education were an advantage.
		Jurnal: Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini (S2)	

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6	(Rasto et al., 2023)	Bibliometric Analysis: Management in Early Childhood Education	Since 2016, publications on early childhood and teacher training have increased, with the US contributing 20% of global publications, according to a bibliometric analysis.		Their Support by Current Neuroscience	preschool children through spontaneous repetition, aligning with neurodevelopmental processes like early sensory and motor cortice development and synaptic pruning. Recent research highlights Montessori's contribution to language and the benefits of physical exercise on the brain.	
7	(Firman & Ali, 2023)	Perencanaan Strategis dalam Pengelolaan Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini	Strategic planning involves identifying needs, conducting research, establishing a vision, creating programs, and creating documents and plans to achieve long-term and short-term goals in early childhood education.	10	(D'Amico et al., 2023)	Examining Early Childhood Education through the Lens of Stakeholders: A Statewide Needs Assessment	The needs of families with diverse racial, ethnic and linguistic backgrounds. Black parents, both those with a college education and those working part-time, prioritize home teaching, and parents who work and have advanced degrees prioritize home teaching. Thus, Black parents prioritize having more time to play with their children.
8	(Yulianingsih et al., 2020)	Keterlibatan Orangtua dalam Pendampingan Belajar Anak selama Masa Pandemi Covid-19	Research indicates that parents play a crucial role in children's learning, fulfilling their needs, providing spiritual guidance, supervision, incentives, and facilities.			Jurnal: Journal of Early Childhood Research (Q1)	
9	(Catherine et al., 2020)	Four Pillars of the Montessori Method and	Montessori's model promotes sensory education in	11	(Schriever, 2021)	Early Childhood Teacher's Perceptions and Management of Parental Concerns	Early childhood teachers in kindergarten face parental concerns about their children's digital technology use.

		About Their Differences Child's between home Digital and kindergarten Technology environments Use in affect access, Kindergarten expectations, and mediation Jurnal: Journal of Teachers educate Early of parents about Childhood digital Research (Q1) technology use in kindergarten.			Elementary from 70.00 to School 95.00 in the first Jurnal: cycle through Jurnal Ilmiah testing research Sekolah Dasar instruments, (S2) observing learning processes, and conducting assessments.	
12	(Herlina et al., 2023)	Eksplorasi The study Fenomena reveals Supervisi challenges in Akademik implementing pada Satuan academic Pendidikan supervision in Anak Usia kindergarten, Dini including Jurnal: planning, scope, Jurnal Obsesi : and influencing Jurnal factors, and can Pendidikan serve as a policy Anak Usia reference for Dini (S2) schools and education departments.		15	(Basuki & Perdinanto, 2023)	The Role of The study School reveals a positive Supervisors in correlation Encouraging between Teachers to supervisors' role Manage and teacher Postflood motivation, Recovery highlighting Actions their crucial role Jurnal: in school Journal of management, Educational flood mitigation, and Social and encouraging Research (Q3) teachers to continue teaching and learning.
13	(Ali & May, 2023)	Studi The study Komparisasi reveals Pelaksanaan significant Supervisi differences in Guru di supervision Finlandia dan goals, Cina sebagai supervisors, Negara Maju implementation Jurnal: strategies, and Jurnal Obsesi : final results Jurnal between Finland Pendidikan and China, Anak Usia highlighting the Dini (S2) need for education policymakers to consider these findings.		16	(Fosu- Ayarkwah et al., 2022)	Effects of The study Teacher's suggests that Supervision increased teacher on the Safety supervision in of schools can Kindergarten improve student Pupils in the comfort, safety, Central academic Region of achievement, Ghana reduce fear, Jurnal: promote Open Journal teaching, and of Educational encourage play Research (Q1) experiences.
14	(Babo & Syamsuddin, 2022)	Clinical Clinical Supervision supervision Model to improved Improve the teacher learning Qualitu of quality by Learning in increasing learning scores		17	(Belan & Niron, 2021)	Academic The research Supervision of results show that School the principal's Principals, academic Principal supervision Transformatio influences nal teacher abilities; Leadership, the principal's and School transformational Climate on leadership also Senior High influences School teacher abilities; and school

		Teacher's climate also Competence influences the Jurnal: ability of Al-Ishlah: teachers in Jurnal Lembata. Pendidikan (S2)			Teacher's issue involving Views of teachers' lives, Supervision in practicum Early environments, Childhood ECTE programs, Teacher and the Finnish Education educational Practicums system. It Jurnal: identifies six Teaching and frameworks for Teacher understanding Education supervision, (Q1) addressing challenges and enhancing comprehension.		
18	(Halmaida et al., 2022)	Implementatio n of Academic Supervision and Teacher Performance Assesment Jurnal: Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan (S2)	The research reveals that academic supervision programs and teacher performance assessments identify issues, provide training, and assist teachers, while the principal evaluates job descriptions and evidence for deficiencies.	21	(Soro et al., 2023)	Analysis of Academic Supervision Competence through Workshop Activities (Case Study of Kapuas District Islamic Religious Education Teachers) Jurnal: QALAMUNA : Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, Dan Agama (S2)	The research indicates that well-planned and executed workshop activities enhance academic supervision competence and supervisor experience, providing new knowledge and experiences for both supervisors and teachers.
19	(Mahfud et al., 2023)	Planning for Principal Supervision in Improving the Performance of Educators and Education Personnel (Multisite Study at SMPIT Ar Rahmah Pacitan and MTs Al Anwar Pacitan) Jurnal: International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies (Copernicus)	The research suggests that school principals can enhance educator and staff performance by implementing supervision programs, budgeting, and forming support teams. It modifies Louis A. Allen's planning theory, excluding program outreach and goal setting.	22	(Dwikurnaning sih & Paais, 2022)	Principal Academic Supervision: Performance, Problems and Solutions Jurnal: Jurnal Pendidikan Indonesia (S2)	The research indicates that school principals' performance in planning, implementation, and follow-up stages of academic supervision is low, suggesting a collaborative supervision model as a suitable solution.
20	(Puroila et al., 2021)	Multiple Facets of Supervision: Cooperative	The study reveals supervision is a multifaceted	23	(Chaula, 2024)	Measure for Clinical	The study suggests that

		Supervision clinical Practices as supervision Factors of adjustment can Predictive of enhance teacher Indicators of professional Teacher's identity development, Identity urging Development government in Tanzania innovation in JURNAL: clinical Heliyon (Q1) supervision practices to promote professional growth.			teachers' motivation and acceptance of supervision are crucial factors in improving teaching quality. Directive supervision, particularly for beginners, can positively impact teacher attitudes, especially when implemented sincerely.		
24	(Brown et al., 2020)	“Kindergarten Isn’t Fun Anymore. Isn’t that so sad?”: Examining How Kindergarten Teachers in the US Made Sense of the Changed Kindergarten Teaching and Teacher Education (Q1)	Kindergarten teachers believe it prepares children for later grades by reducing assessment demands. They want to transform kindergarten by providing more engaging learning activities and teaching the 'whole child'. However, they question the feasibility of such changes and worry about the future of teachers and the future of kindergarten reform.	26	(Turos, 2024)	Comparative Analysis of The Views of Montessori and Waldorf Teacher Trainers Jurnal: Social Sciences & Humanities Open (Q4)	Montessori and Waldorf pedagogy differ in theoretical aspects such as intellect, developmental methods, art, imagination, movement, scientific criteria, and attitudes towards modern ICT technology, with Hungary implementing the most Waldorf schools. Effective supervision in education involves strong leaders who foster a positive classroom culture, practice clear communication, develop shared goals, learn evidence-based practices, regularly observe, coach, and create accountability-
25	(Hoque et al., 2020)	Relationships Between Supervision and Teacher's Performance and Attitude in Secondary Schools in Malaysia	The study suggests that developmental monitoring methods and directive supervision do not significantly influence teacher attitudes, indicating that	27	(Bagawan et al., 2023)	Components of Effective Supervision and Training for Paraeducators Jurnal: Intervention in School and Clinic-Sage Journal (Q2)	Effective supervision in education involves strong leaders who foster a positive classroom culture, practice clear communication, develop shared goals, learn evidence-based practices, regularly observe, coach, and create accountability-

33	(Beach, 2023)	<p>Research on Montessori Early Literacy in Reggio and Montessori Classrooms: A Scoping Review Jurnal: Journal of Early Childhood Literacy (Q2)</p> <p>Research on Montessori teacher guides guide children through inquiry, play, and art, promoting literacy through inquiry, play, and art. Research in Reggio and Montessori contexts emphasizes language-rich environments and spoken language development. Montessori and Reggio early childhood literacy programs benefit children.</p>	<p>Current Directions in Psychological Science (Q1)</p>	<p>is school certification. The Association Montessori Internationale (AMI) was founded by Montessori to carry out her work; therefore, research conducted in AMI-certified schools may reflect authentic implementation. Many schools that call themselves Montessori deviate from implementing AMI. Children in Montessori programs fared better or equally on every variable tested—never worse. 5-year-olds performed better on tests of reading, mathematics, executive function, social understanding, and moral reasoning. On the playground, they engage in shared play with more positive peers and less aggressive play</p>
34	(Gynther & Ahlquist, 2022)	<p>Education for Sustainability and Global Citizenship for 6-12 Year Olds in Montessori Education Jurnal: Journal of Education for Sustainable Development</p> <p>Montessori education provides children with an emotional connection to a universal approach, fostering empowerment. It is a democratic teaching tradition with a focus on didactic application of materials. Montessori teacher training programs focus on developing knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values for a sustainable future.</p>	<p>36 (Demangeon et al., 2023)</p>	<p>A Meta-Analysis of the Effects of Montessori Education on Five Fields of Development and Learning in Preschool</p> <p>The results show that the influence of Montessori education on development and learning is positive and varies from moderate to</p>
35	(Lillard, 2018)	<p>Rethinking Education: Montessori's Approach Jurnal:</p> <p>One guarantee of high-quality Montessori implementation</p>		

		and School-Age Children Jurnal: Contemporary Educational Psychology (Q1)	high, depending on the dimensions considered			in the Czech Republic Jurnal: Issues in Educational Research (Q2)	supervisors, focusing on respecting children's development and individuality. This unique identity is influenced by personal beliefs and values, fostering a supportive environment for exploration and learning.	
37	(Gentaz & Richard, 2022)	The Behavioral Effects of Montessori Pedagogy on Children's Psychological Development and School Learning Jurnal: Children (Q2)	Montessori education enhances cognitive flexibility, academic skills, social cognition, and enjoyment of academic assignments compared to conventional classes, with students at all grade levels reporting higher performance.					
38	(Marshall, 2017a)	Montessori Education: A Review of the Evidence Base Jurnal: Npj Science of Learning (Q1)	Montessori education focuses on children's intellectual, physical, emotional, and social development through real-life learning materials, including activities like gardening, and uses touch boards, sandpaper letters, and pink towers for independent living skills.			40 (Macià-Gual & Domingo-Peñañiel, 2023)	Analysing the Montessori Principles from the Perspective of Schools, Teachers, and Families Jurnal: Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal (Q3)	Montessori principles are integral to pedagogy, requiring extensive training to enhance early childhood education practices, requiring collaboration between families and schools for optimal implementation. When compared with traditional educational approaches, Montessori education has a significant and positive effect on children's academic and non-academic achievements.
39	(Jurčik, 2023)	Freedom and Respect: Who are the Montessori School Teachers? A Teacher Identity Study	Montessori teachers' professional identity is shaped by their role as creators of a ready-to-use environment and			41 (Randolph et al., 2023)	Montessori Education's Impact on Academic and Nonacademic Outcomes: A Systematic Review Jurnal: Campbell Systematic Reviews (Q1)	
						42 (Sağlam et al., 2023)	Meta-Thematic Analysis of Early Childhood Education and Care	The analysis identified 16 quality indicators for early childhood education and care, including child-

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	Education and Care	Jurnal: Humanities & Social Sciences Communications (Q1)	centeredness, qualified teachers, center culture, holistic development, and leadership. Cultural values, centralization, and stakeholder expectations also influence quality perceptions in PAUD.		Childhood Education	differs from Waldorf and Reggio Emilia in terms of teacher number and classroom setup. Montessori teachers act as observers, while Reggio Emilia teachers participate more in discussions.			
43	(Denervaud et al., 2020)	An FMRI Study of Error Monitoring in Montessori and Traditionally-Schooled Children	Journal: NPJ Science of Learning (Q1)	These findings suggest that pedagogical experiences influence the development of error monitoring and its neural correlates, with implications for neurodevelopment and education.	46	(Astutik & Roesminingsih, 2021)	The Improvement of Teacher's Professional Competency through HOTS-Based Training	Journal: Pendidikan Indonesia (JPI) (Sinta 2)	The study reveals that HOTS training significantly enhances teachers' professional abilities, highlighting the need for further research to optimize policy framework models and theoretical frameworks.
44	(Chen, 2021)	Exploration of Implementation Practices of Montessori Education in Mainland China	Journal: Humanities & Social Sciences Communications (Q1)	Montessori education in Chinese classrooms is influenced by high-fidelity Montessori practices, with mixed classrooms and co-teaching classrooms exhibiting different outcomes. Localization and sustainability are crucial for sustainability.	47	(Heni et al., 2023)	The Effectiveness of Neuroscience to Improve Teacher Pedagogic Competence: Systematic Literature Review	Journal: Pendidikan Indonesia (JPI) (Sinta 2)	The study suggests that teachers can enhance their teaching skills by gaining a deeper understanding of neuroscience, which aids in understanding student characteristics, learning theories, and educational principles.
45	(Aljabreen, 2020)	Montessori, Waldorf, and Reggio Emilia: A Comparative Analysis of Alternative Models of Early		Montessori education is a unique approach that emphasizes reading and writing, using materials designed over a century ago. It	48	(Demangeon et al., 2023)	A Meta-Analysis of		The results show that, depending

	<p>the Effects of on the Montessori dimensions Education on considered: Five Fields of cognitive Development abilities (g = and Learning 0.17), social in Preschool skills (g = 0.22), and School creativity (g = Age Children 0.25), motor Jurnal: skills (g = 0.27), Contemporary and academic Educational achievement (g = Psychology 1.10), the (Q1) influence of ME on development and learning is positive and varies from moderate to high. No differences by school level, publication type, or continent were found in the different moderator analyses.</p>		<p>50 .</p>	<p>However, SOF became more independent, confident, and flexible. Teacher-led evaluation leads to positive motivation and practice change, particularly in content knowledge assessment and test score data analysis, while principals' use of extrinsic motivation tools negatively affects motivation.</p>
<p>49 (Opiola et al., 2020)</p>	<p>The Effectiveness of Training and Supervising Urban Elementary School Teachers in Child-Teacher Relationship Training: A Trauma-Informed Approach Jurnal: Professional School Counseling Sage Journal</p> <p>The study found that after training, teachers became more emotionally attuned to their Somatic Orientation (SOF) and students' behavior, focusing on emotional regulation. Teachers who received CTRT had a positive relationship with SOF. Participants' attitudes towards SOF behavior decreased, and they reported a decrease in stress and anxiety.</p>			

Based on the results in Table 1, a model of the findings of this research can be formulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Supervision using the Montessori Method

Supervision Prerequisites		
Supervision using the Montessori Method		
Knowledge	Interpersonal Skills	Technical Skills
Self-education, freedom, activity, movement, practical experience, psychological and biological develop through sensitive periods, stimulation of intellectual, physical, emotional and social development.	Good communication, soft skills, brainstorming	Guidance directly, group development, Professional development (through AMI, namely Association Montessori Internationale), curriculum development, action research, facilitating change, addressing diversity, building community.
Montessori has 4 conceptual pillars of the Montessori		

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<p>method, namely: (1) Sensitive Periods, (2) Education of Senses, (3) Preparation of Environment, (4) Spontaneous through Activities</p> <p>Nine elements of Montessori: (1) Montessori involves direct learning, cognition and movement, using materials, (2) Montessori students can pursue what interests them, so they can achieve a positive feeling or sense of well-being at school (3) Montessori students choose what they like. what they want to learn at that time, based on research, children who have an environment that can make them decide for themselves, then academics will improve, (4) Montessori also places a high priority on concentrated attention and developing executive functions, (5) Learning comes</p>			<p>from intrinsic motivation, (6) Montessori learning learns with concrete objects, (7) Children can work with their peers, they will learn imitation and collaboration, (8) Montessori teachers are directed to work with children in specific ways and provide facilities for children to encourage creativity to solve problems , (9) The Montessori environment is strictly organized, with everything in its place, there is order</p>		
			<p>Result</p>	<p>Learning or stimulating aspects of children's development increases as a goal of school</p> <p>Teacher management indicators consist of: (1) technical competency in educational planning for ECE managers and teachers; (2) coaching competency through personality, attitudes, behavior of ECE managers and teachers; (3) competence in processing and analyzing academic data; ECE social, religious and psychological competencies for the learning process and administration of ECE managers and teachers; and (4) scientific guidance for the development of the ECE curriculum for ECE managers and teachers</p> <p>Aspects of child development that are given stimulation: (1) cognitive, (2) physical, (3) motoric, (4) sensory, (5)</p>	

social, (6) emotional, (7) moral, (8) religious, (9) art, (10) language.
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IV. DISCUSSION

Kindergarten Teacher Supervision Strategy

Supervision is a strategy that teachers can use to improve both their teaching abilities and their students' learning. In Indonesia, education assessment is carried out by monitoring and evaluation activities (Monev) or by education and evaluation supervisors accredited by the National Accreditation Board (BAN). Effective coordination between institutions and associated supervisors is required since supervision is one method for evaluating education and learning management and improving quality (Utami et al., 2020). School principals are responsible for educating, managing, administering, supervising, leading, innovating, and motivating. They must also ensure that early childhood education is delivered effectively by ongoing and systematic planning, organization, direction, and supervision (Pujiyati, 2021). The process in which assessments are conducted determines how teachers perceive their feedback and how it inspires (or does not motivate) adjustments in practice (Ford & Lavigne, 2023).

The principal serves as supervisor for teacher evaluations. In recent years, the role of principal has become increasingly difficult (Ford & Lavigne, 2023). Academic supervision provided by the school principal is internal academic supervision. Educational supervision is the process of establishing and enhancing educational processes with the goal of improving teachers' abilities, performance, and expertise (Herlina et al., 2023). Academic supervision provided by school principals has a substantial impact on pedagogy and professional competency teacher performance (Belan & Niron, 2021). Teacher supervision is concerned with learning preparation, implementation, and evaluation (Babo & Syamsuddin, 2022).

Teachers must be pedagogically competent, which involves comprehending all elements of their students: physical, moral, social, cultural, emotional, and intellectual (Heni et al., 2023). Supervision can begin with a pre-supervision process, planning, and implementation, which may involve workshops, assessments, and follow-up plans. School principals and senior instructors can help implement supervision (Firman & Ali, 2023). Motivation (the teacher feels he can accomplish more, receives support, and has the children's trust), creativity (the teacher has fresh ideas, actively develops new learning ideas, and has new ways to teach), and innovation (the teacher works with different parties to develop learning models, takes the school environment into consideration, and has access to enough resources to do so) are all influenced by supervision (Basuki & Perdinanto, 2023). Based on learning, supervision—which can be done in a collaborative or collegial setting—affects how well teacher's function. Improving teacher talents is

more successful in a supervision procedure that prioritizes equality of position between supervisors and teachers; this is because balancing the responsibilities of supervisor and teacher will improve slowness, feedback, mutual aid, and idea expression. Objectives for supervision can be met and effectively bridged (Wiyono et al., 2021).

Process requirements, subject standards (Bachelor of Early Childhood Education), and teaching are all included in academic supervision. Under the supervision of the principle, the Daily Learning Implementation Plan (RPPH) material's suitability for use with learning media is evaluated, together with the instructor's capacity to adapt the lesson to the student's age, class mastery, and teacher evaluation (Herlina et al., 2023).

In addition to providing space for children to be creative, teachers also need to be aware of the requirements of the students regarding learning strategies, resources, and media. Subsequently, the educator needs to design a lesson plan that satisfies the following early childhood education requirements: (1) perception; (2) concreteness; (3) motivation; (4) working independently; (5) working collaboratively; (6) individualization; (7) correlation; and (8) elements of lifelong learning concepts. Teachers also have a responsibility to attend to the needs and safety of the students (Utami et al., 2020). All teachers must establish a social environment that supports effective teaching and learning processes and be aware about potential hazards to promote school safety (Fosu-Ayarkwah et al., 2022). Pedagogy, child stimulation educational material, and teacher modification are all things that teachers need to know. Because student behavior affects the teacher's ability to manage the classroom climate and because the emotional environment of the classroom influences student learning and teacher vitality, it is crucial for teachers to strengthen their relationships with their students and pay attention to students who are experiencing particular emotional states, according to Opiola's research, CTRT (Child-Teacher Relationship Training) interventions can help with this. Teachers who consistently have positive experiences in the classroom and feel good about themselves will be more resilient, motivated, and able to handle a variety of demands that come at once (Opiola et al., 2020). According to Yang et al., teachers frequently observe that students struggle to control their emotions and express their thoughts. Some students even have tantrums, crying, screaming, biting, and hitting. For this reason, teachers must provide resources for emotional management, such as behavioral self-regulation, conflict resolution skills, and the ability to recognize emotions in their students (Yang et al., 2021).

It is stated that strong leaders and supervisors are essential for educators. Strong leaders who cultivate a positive classroom/team culture and practice clear communication, goal setting, learning evidence-based practices, frequent observation, coaching with feedback, and

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building a community that promotes accountability are the key to effective supervision (Bagawan et al., 2023).

Teacher management indicators consist of: (1) technical competency in educational planning for ECE managers and teachers; (2) coaching competency through personality, attitudes, behaviour of ECE managers and teachers; (3) competence in processing and analyzing academic data; ECE social, religious and psychological competencies for the learning process and administration of ECE managers and teachers; and (4) scientific guidance for the development of the ECE curriculum for ECE managers and teachers (Botutihe, 2020).

Teacher competency includes both intellectual and soft skills. Soft skills include communication, time management, negotiation, writing, listening, reading, and decision making, as well as self-regulation, self-awareness, and the ability to create and sustain strong and healthy connections with peers (Rasmani et al., 2021). Sağlam et al. define teacher professional development as collaborative networks, mentoring, and continual development (Sağlam et al., 2023).

The strategy focuses on high-quality early childhood care and education, a healthy professional culture, and the empowerment of early childhood educators. One crucial strategy for achieving these goals is to recruit, support, and retain high-quality teachers. This process entails coaching and mentoring teachers, demonstrating high-quality classroom practice modules, managing children's behaviour, and using technology. Other strategies to achieve these goals include increasing living wages and professional benefits for the workforce, professionalizing the role of early childhood educators, strengthening, and diversifying the teacher workforce, retaining effective teachers, and expanding quality improvement initiatives. Strategies employed include educating staff/teachers in childcare/early education settings to support children with disabilities, evaluating program regulations in accepting children with disabilities, and providing appropriate environments and supports (D'Amico et al., 2023).

Early childhood teachers play a significant role in classroom organization (Schriever, 2021). Teaching methods in early childhood education refer to the National Standards for Early Childhood Education (SN PAUD), namely Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 137 of 2014. Learning methods can be by storytelling, demonstrations to improve cognitive and fine motor skills, field trips to stimulate abilities. children's storytelling and gross motor skills (Pujiyati, 2021). Early childhood teachers must manage parents' expectations about the role of ICT in kindergarten, namely the extent to which their children will be exposed to and use digital devices (Schriever, 2021).

Implementation of Learning using the Montessori Method

Montessori views learning as a holistic process in which all children grow physically, cognitively, socially, and emotionally. The Montessori method is based on the notion that children should learn in a pleasant setting that gives them freedom of movement, choice, and personal responsibility. Teacher guides and curriculum materials on the Montessori approach have been developed to assist teachers and school administrators in establishing Montessori schools and executing the curriculum (Beach, 2023). According to Montessori, children are spiritual embryos whose psychological and biological development occur concurrently throughout sensitive periods in which children are interested in and willing to accept particular areas and acquire a variety of special skills and abilities. Montessori's theory holds that the environment influences the microenvironment of the brain in children and can even extend the key period of brain plasticity into adulthood. Another notable observation is the importance of manipulating fine objects in neuropsychological development, which led Montessori to state that "the hand is the organ of the brain," This intuition has also been verified. Brain mapping studies have revealed that the motor and sensory cortical regions utilized to represent the hand are larger than the hand itself, indicating that a high number of neurons are involved in directing movement and processing sensory information. Hand mobility is so vital that its restrictions can have serious consequences, such as the discovery that children who use tablets from a young age have delayed language development (Fabri & Fortuna, 2020).

The Montessori model also incorporates Abraham Maslow's psychology, which emphasizes the significance of addressing a child's total developmental requirements through experiences in a natural learning environment. Montessori serves as a guide, assisting children in developing relationships with one another, developing discipline and self-control, independently focusing on the child's interests and using materials, and being guided in the fields of practical life, sensory, mathematics, language, science and geography, art, and music (Aljabreen, 2020).

Montessori maintained that children go through sensitive learning periods and phases of development, and that engaging in independent activities in carefully prepared environments might help them form their own identities (Marshall, 2017). The atmosphere is designed to allow children to act freely and independently of adults (within a reasonable framework), enhancing their autonomy, initiative, and ability to achieve profound concentration. The utilization of equipment not only allows for mobility, but it also helps kids channel their movement requirements. Then, because the materials used by children are self-correcting, kids receive rapid feedback on their progress, with no adult interference (Gentaz & Richard, 2022).

Across conditions, Montessori students had higher brain activity than traditionally schooled students in regions involved in visual and mathematical processing, as well as regions associated with attentional/executive control, indicating a more exploratory, self-correcting, and multisensory approach to mathematical cognitive processes (Denervaud et al., 2020). Montessori education has a positive effect on growth and learning, ranging from moderate to high levels (Demangeon et al., 2023).

Montessori ideas aim to help children develop individually (Macià-Gual & Domingo-Peñañiel, 2023). Montessori's method is based on four conceptual pillars: (1) sensitive periods, (2) sensory education, (3) environmental preparation, and (4) spontaneous activities (Catherine et al., 2020). Montessori emphasizes that her technique is scientific in terms of its goals and substance; if science is utilized to improve children's physical growth, then facilities for children's emotional development must also use scientific and rational methods. Montessori classifies the functions that must be identified into motor functions and sensory functions (Montessori, 2020).

Montessori has nine elements: (1) direct learning, cognition, and movement, using materials. (2) Montessori pupils can explore what interests them, resulting in a happy feeling or sense of well-being at school. (3) Montessori children select what they want. According to study, children who live in an atmosphere that allows them to make their own decisions will perform better in school. (4) Montessori also prioritizes focused attention and the development of executive functions. (5) Learning stems from intrinsic drive. (6) Montessori learning uses concrete objects. (7) Children can work with their peers, learning imitation and collaboration. (8) Montessori teachers are directed to interact with children in specific ways and give resources for children to stimulate creativity in problem solving. (9) The Montessori environment is strictly organized, with everything in its place and order (Randolph et al., 2023).

In a Montessori classroom, the first learning materials a child may meet are those that comprise a curriculum centered on real life. This involves pouring different materials, cleaning and polishing, making snacks, setting the table and washing dishes, arranging flowers, gardening, straightening and untying garments, and so on. To introduce children to the cycle of choosing, starting, finishing, and tidying up an activity, in addition to improving their independent living skills, the goal is to improve hand-eye coordination and gross and fine motor control (which will be explained further in the following section), and to establish rules that allow them to operate within the class's social environment (Marshall, 2017).

Montessori education has a direct impact on children's intellectual development beginning in kindergarten. For Montessori, work and play are inextricably linked, providing a natural and enjoyable approach for

children to learn by touching and moving solid objects rather than simply memorizing them (Lillard, 2021). Learning is divided into sensory stimulation using knobbed cylinders, pink towers, brown stairs, numbers rods, touch boards, baric tablets, colour tablets, geometric tablets, geometric cabinets, geometric cards, etc., preparatory learning for writing and arithmetic using sandpaper letters and sandpaper numbers, learning to care for yourself, learning to care for the environment, gardening, fostering creativity, learning body coordination, rhythmic movements (Montessori, 2020). The Montessori system divides learning into three stages (naming, recognizing, and recalling) (Paramita, 2020).

A Montessori school teacher's professional identity is primarily impacted by: (1) approach to children's education; in the classroom, children play while learning and tidying up their work. (2) Personal experience, a person's professional identity is established in reference to their own experience over many years as a student. (3) Definition in relation to the unknown, many teachers' responses have a very lengthy view of experience (Jurčík, 2023).

The quality of Montessori schools is determined by the Association Montessori Internationale (AMI), based on research explanations that children who take part in the Montessori program are superior in tests of reading, mathematics, executive function, social understanding and moral reasoning, in the playground playing effectively and not aggressively, one of the aspects What is surprising is that children concentrate on their work for periods of time often exceeding 30 minutes (Lillard, 2018).

Teacher Supervision Strategies to Maintain Learning Quality using the Montessori Method

Supervision prerequisites are knowledge, interpersonal skills, and technical skills (Glickman, Carl D, Stephen P. Gordon, 2013). Supervision can begin with a pre-supervision process, followed by planning, implementation (sometimes including workshop activities), evaluation, and follow-up plans. School principals and senior teachers can help implement supervision (Firman & Ali, 2023). So, if the school adopts the Montessori method, teachers can participate in Montessori-related workshops or training, beginning with an overview of the Montessori method's four pillars, three stages of learning, and Montessori's media.

Teacher management indicators include: (1) technical competency in educational planning for PAUD managers and teachers; (2) coaching competency through personality, attitudes, and behaviour of PAUD managers and teachers; (3) competence in processing and analysing academic data; PAUD social, religious, and psychological competencies for the learning process and administration of PAUD managers and teachers; and (4) scientific guidance for the development of PAUD curricula (Botutihe, 2020). Teachers should prioritize the needs of their students by reorienting their teaching approach to include more

possibilities for students to participate actively in their education (Thompson & Stanković-Ramirez, 2021).

According to Montessori, children's development can be impeded if there is no stimulus since they are in a sensitive stage that cannot be reached in the following stage. Yi-Huang Shih outlined the necessity of a love-based relationship between educators and students, then made a connection between this approach and Montessori's theory of children's sensitive periods and the concentration that occurs when children make their own decisions. The following are the techniques: PAUD teachers' hearts should be filled with love; (2) preschool teachers and early childhood students should have a loving relationship; (3) opportunities should be provided for young children to practice affectionate behaviour; (4) young children should be given freedom; (5) open dialogue should be maintained; (6) emphasize democratic participation; (7) avoid indoctrination; (8) respecting young children's experiences and discoveries; (9) letting young children make choices and (10) understanding young children as individuals (Shih, 2022).

The application of Montessori materials in education is the main focus of Montessori teacher training programs, schools play a significant role in supplying the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that enable society to contribute to a sustainable future. Montessori emphasizes that teachers have a responsibility to gain in-depth knowledge of subjects that may go beyond the requirements of the curriculum in order to engage students by drawing on their imaginations, she highlighted that teaching must make the most of students' capacity for imagination and visualization (Gynther & Ahlquist, 2022). Organizations need to employ education and training as one of the most effective strategies for developing their human resources. Gradually altering an individual's knowledge, abilities, attitudes, and conduct, education and training enable educators to attain peak performance (Astutik & Roesminingsih, 2021).

Supervision of Montessori schools and Montessori school teachers must be carried out and supervision must be provided to teachers who have the label "Montessori School". It has been explained that Montessori created a special association to check whether the quality of Montessori schools is appropriate or not, therefore, to give the label "Montessori School" it must comply with AMI standards and teachers must be given training with AMI. AMI has a website. The website explains that the training is divided into several categories starting from Assistant to Infancy for children 0-3 years, Casa dei Bambini/Children's House 3-6 years, elementary for children 6-12 years, adolescent children 12-18 years and there is a sports program category, dementia, disability and aging, Montessori administrators and parent engagement. So kindergarten schools must choose the Casa dei Bambini/Children's House program. Montessori teacher training in Indonesia, some of which are recognized by DIKNAS, include: (1) Sunshine Teacher's Training, (2)

Modern Montessori International Indonesia (MMI Indonesia), (3) Cosmic Montessori Institute, (4) Montessori HAUS Asia, (5) Asia Montessori Institute (AMI).

V. CONCLUSION

Research found that many schools label themselves as "Montessori Schools" but many do not meet the standards. Meanwhile, early childhood education is a crucial age for implementing stimulus because it is a sensitive period and a golden age. Teachers are child educators who provide stimulation, so that "Montessori Schools" must be given supervision regarding teacher supervision. The results of this research: In Indonesia, educational evaluation is carried out through monitoring and evaluation activities (Monev) or supervision carried out by education and evaluation supervisors who are accredited by the National Accreditation Agency (BAN), then learning using the Montessori Method has 4 pillar concepts and 9 elements, and The supervision strategy using the Montessori method for teachers is that the prerequisites are supervision with knowledge, interpersonal skills and technical skills.

The research recommendation is to carry out research in the field and use SLR as a reference and can be used as evidence, because the limitations of SLR are theoretical so empirical evidence is needed to dig deeper into research in the field.

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VII. DISCLOSURE

The author reports no conflicts of interest in this work.

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